

Phase transition in potassium hydrogen phthalate crystals – effect of various molar concentration of L-Glutamine

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Abstract:

This paper Investigate the crystalline nature of potassium hydrogen phthalate crystals when added with L-Glutamine in three different molar concentrations prepared by the slow evaporation method and characterized by Ultraviolet spectrum, Fourier Transform of Infrared spectrum and Powder x-ray diffraction techniques. Calculated energy show that there is a loss of energy due to the inelastic scattering occurs in UV analysis. The phase transition occurs due the variation in concentration of L-Glutamine. As the concentration increases the increased concentration changes the crystal system of grown crystals. The cell parameters, particle size, systematic absences analysed by powder peak pattern of this crystals. The Size and Strain graph plot of Williamson-Hall plot and crystalline size distribution graph of Warren-Aver Bach method interprets strain coefficient, size coefficient and L graph of $(\Delta d/d) \%$ versus length of peaks pattern predicted by Powder X-ray diffraction data.

Keywords: UV-Vis, FT-IR, PXRD, Williamson-Hall Plot, Warren-Aver Bach Method.

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